

Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms (LUTS) in Patients Treated with Tamsulosin at a Second Level Hospital in Veracruz Mexico.

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ABSTRACT

In Mexico, benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) has been documented as one of the most frequent pathologies in men over 50 years old, being the most common benign tumor in males. Sixty-one percent of the male population present lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) starting at age 40, and it is estimated that 80% of these symptoms are caused by BPH. It has been observed that patients with BPH may experience an impact on their quality of life, both in their family and professional environments, BPH represents the most frequent disease in the urology service and the second Surgical procedure in our country.

Methodology: Observational, descriptive, cross-sectional, prospective study, a sample of 50 patients from the urology outpatient clinic was made and the IPSS Score instrument was applied in addition to adding an additional question in which the patient's interest in undergoing surgical treatment was sought. Descriptive and inferential statistics were performed for the variables of interest.

Conclusions: With increasing age, symptoms tend to become more severe, only 18% of patients (9 of them), with an average of 4.98 years of tamsulosin use, achieved good symptom control, reaching mild stages, Most patients continued to have moderate to severe symptoms, without achieving complete reversal of symptoms, the more severe the symptoms, the more difficult it is to achieve good control with drug treatment, and the likelihood of requiring surgical treatment increases, Although most patients express interest in undergoing transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP), there are barriers such as myths, fear, and indifference that limit acceptance of the surgery.

KEYWORDS: Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia, IPSS, Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The prostate is a fibromuscular and glandular organ that produces a liquid secretion forming part of semen. This secretion contains substances that provide nutrients and an adequate medium for sperm survival. The prostate consists of three main zones: the central zone, the peripheral zone, and the transitional zone. Prostatic pathology is one of the most frequent reasons for consultation in family medicine and urology.

I.1 Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH): definition and epidemiology.

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a common condition in older men, characterized by a non-cancerous enlargement of the prostate gland. It represents the most prevalent benign tumor in men over 50 years of age. This uncontrolled growth may compress the urethra and cause lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS), such as difficulty initiating urination, weak urinary stream, and frequent urination, especially at

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night. It is estimated that more than 50% of men over 60 years present symptoms related to BPH.

BPH affects approximately 50% of the global male population over 50 years of age, particularly those between 65 and 80 years. In Mexico, the incidence is 424.86 cases per 100,000 inhabitants, with a prevalence of 3,873.73 per 100,000 men. Prevalence varies depending on the population studied. According to the Olmsted County Study, LUTS increase progressively from moderate to severe, affecting nearly 50% of men by the age of 70. The presence of these symptoms is associated with acute urinary retention as a clinical manifestation of benign prostatic growth. Around 8% of men at age 40 present BPH, while half of men between 50 and 60 years have histological evidence of the disease. The estimated doubling time of prostatic growth in BPH is 4.5 years between ages 31 and 50, and 10 years between ages 51 and 70.

In Mexico, BPH represents the second leading cause of surgical intervention and the first cause of urological consultation. Its prevalence increases with age, and approximately 6 out of 10 Mexican men over 55 years old will present LUTS. Of these, 25% suffer obstructive symptoms, and by age 75, half report decreased urinary stream strength and caliber.

I.2 LUTS, or Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms.

LUTS are a variety of discomforts attributable to this anatomical region and represent a subjective indicator of change or dysfunction as perceived by the patient, caregiver, or partner. They may lead patients to seek medical attention. These symptoms are qualitative, may be the main reason for consultation or arise during anamnesis. However, they are generally not sufficient for a definitive diagnosis and can also suggest other pathologies, such as urinary tract infections.

LUTS can be grouped according to the phase of the micturition cycle in which they occur:

Storage (filling) symptoms: May be caused by bladder dysfunction (e.g., detrusor overactivity or impaired contractility) or adaptive bladder changes associated with benign prostatic obstruction, often due to prostatic enlargement. Typical symptoms include pollakiuria, nocturia, urgency, urge incontinence, or bladder pain during filling. These alterations affect both the bladder and an overactive detrusor muscle. **Voiding symptoms** include weak stream, hesitancy, straining, terminal dribbling, and acute urinary retention. These are mainly attributable to obstructive phenomena, such as urethral stricture or, more commonly, BPH, which is the leading etiology of this symptom group and post-micturition symptoms may coexist with storage and voiding symptoms in BPH and may appear in various combinations. Their presentation is often nonspecific and may also be the result of central or peripheral nervous system dysfunction, although these causes are less frequent.

I.3 Pathophysiology of Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH).

BPH corresponds to a histological phenomenon that leads to the continuous and progressive enlargement of the prostate. Although it is highly prevalent, there are no universally agreed diagnostic criteria. BPH is one of the most frequent diseases in men over 50 years of age, and its prevalence increases progressively with age.

The average age of symptom onset is around 45 years, with both frequency and severity of symptoms increasing between 60 and 65 years. Additional factors such as obesity further raise the risk of developing the condition.

The pathophysiology of BPH involves several key factors, most notably age. It is well established that beyond 50 years of age, the likelihood of developing BPH increases due to age-related changes and gradual prostatic volume enlargement. However, the androgen system and androgen receptor signaling also play essential roles in BPH development. Locally generated dihydrotestosterone (DHT), derived from testosterone via the enzyme 5-alpha-reductase type II, is the primary agent stimulating stromal and epithelial proliferation. This is the rationale behind many pharmacological treatments.

Androgens are essential for the development and maintenance of the prostate. Once formed, DHT binds to androgen receptors in stromal and epithelial cells, activating the transcription of target genes that promote prostatic tissue growth and survival. In BPH pathophysiology, this androgenic stimulation persists, leading to increased cellular proliferation and reduced apoptosis.

Other factors such as prostatic inflammation and metabolic syndrome are also implicated, particularly in chronic prostatic inflammation, which drives further enlargement of the gland. Insulin resistance additionally promotes tissue proliferation, especially in the periurethral and transitional zones. Hyperplasia occurs at both stromal and epithelial levels, with stromal predominance. Increased proliferation, coupled with decreased apoptosis, results in greater prostate volume.

Chronic inflammation is a common finding in the prostatic tissue of men with BPH. Inflammatory infiltrates—mainly lymphocytes and macrophages—are frequently observed in periurethral and transitional zones. These immune cells release inflammatory mediators, primarily cytokines and growth factors, that stimulate stromal and epithelial proliferation, contributing to tissue remodeling and fibrosis. Chronic inflammation is also associated with increased COX-2 expression and other mediators that sustain prostatic enlargement.

I.4 Pharmacological Treatment: Tamsulosin.

The drugs used in the treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia are mainly aimed at acting on the androgen receptor. For the purposes of this research, we will focus on the mechanism of action of alpha-adrenergic blockers,

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specifically tamsulosin, which is the main drug used in BPH management.

Tamsulosin is a competitive and selective antagonist of alpha-1 adrenergic receptors, particularly the alpha-1A and alpha-1D subtypes, which are predominantly located in the prostate and the bladder neck. By blocking these receptors, it inhibits the action of norepinephrine, thereby reducing prostatic smooth muscle contraction, improving urinary flow, and alleviating irritative symptoms.

Tamsulosin has an oral absorption rate of approximately 90% when taken in a fasting state. A standard dose of 0.4 mg achieves peak plasma concentrations between 3.1 and 5.3 ng/ml. Clinically, it significantly improves urinary flow and substantially reduces IPSS (International Prostate Symptom Score) values.

Tamsulosin specifically targets alpha-1 receptors, which account for approximately 70% of prostatic receptors. This allows relaxation of prostatic and bladder neck smooth muscle without significantly affecting blood vessels, resulting in minimal adverse effects. Possible side effects include orthostatic hypotension, dizziness, blurred vision, and fatigue in some cases. However, given the low prevalence of adverse events and the favorable risk-benefit ratio, tamsulosin is considered the first-line therapeutic option for initiating management of LUTS in patients with BPH.

This drug has a favorable safety profile, being the preferred agent due to its lower incidence of vasomotor and cardiovascular side effects compared to other therapeutic options.

1.5 International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS).

To classify the severity of benign prostatic hyperplasia and to guide therapeutic decision-making, the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) was developed as a standardized clinical tool to assess the severity of lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS). It is widely used in clinical practice, both in family medicine and urology, to support diagnosis, monitor disease progression, and evaluate treatment efficacy.

The IPSS consists of 8 questions:

Sensation of incomplete emptying	Urinary frequency
Intermittency of flow	Urgency
Straining to initiate urination	Weak stream
Weak urinary stream	Nocturia

Each of these items is scored from 0 to 5, where 0 = never and 5 = almost always.

One additional question evaluates the patient's perceived quality of life related to urinary symptoms, rated on a 6-point scale from 0 to 6.

Interpretation of IPSS scores:

- 0–7: Mild symptoms, usually no immediate treatment required.
- 8–19: Moderate symptoms, may require pharmacological treatment.
- 20–35: Severe symptoms, candidates for surgical treatment such as transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP).

The IPSS is first applied at baseline to quantify symptom burden, followed by reassessment after treatment to evaluate improvement or progression, thereby guiding further therapeutic decisions.

Patients treated with tamsulosin generally show significant clinical improvement compared to baseline. On average, their IPSS decreases by 5 to 8 points after 4–6 weeks of therapy, which corresponds to improved urinary flow.

In patients with an IPSS of 20–35, the ideal therapeutic option is surgical treatment, most commonly TURP, which is the procedure of choice in severe symptomatic BPH. However, TURP has a retreatment rate of approximately 10% at 5 years. Risk factors associated with surgical treatment failure include advanced age, elevated PSA, prostate volume >50 ml, intravesical lobe, acute urinary retention, and comorbidities such as diabetes and hypertension. TURP is more effective in smaller prostates, often reducing symptoms to a mild IPSS range. Conversely, patients with prior medical treatment failure or poor adherence may not respond adequately to surgery.

It is worth noting that lack of adherence and misconceptions regarding TURP contribute to reluctance among certain patients to undergo surgical treatment, even in the presence of severe symptoms.

II RESULTS

A total of 50 patients with benign prostatic hyperplasia and tamsulosin use for three years or longer were included. The mean age was 71.3 years. There was a higher prevalence of severe symptoms, corresponding to 23 patients (46%), with an average IPSS score of 25.5 points. This was followed by 18 patients (36%) with moderate symptoms, who had an average IPSS score of 15.8, and 9 patients (18%) with mild symptoms, with an average IPSS score of 7.33. The mean age of patients with mild symptoms was 71.3 years, those with moderate symptoms had an average age of 66.4 years, and those with severe symptoms had an average age of 74 years.

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Graph Number 1. Patient Age

A total of 50 patients were surveyed with the average age being 71.3 years. The highest age was 82 years, and the lowest was 58.

We found that in the severity of symptoms according to the IPSS scale, there was a predominance of severe symptoms, with a total of 23 patients with severe symptoms (46%) followed by 18 patients with moderate symptoms (36%) and finally 9 patients with mild symptoms (18%). The International Prostate Symptom Scale (IPSS) classifies patients into 3 groups according to the score obtained, being mild from 0 to 7 points, moderate from 8 to 19 points and severe from 20 to 35.

According to the International IPSS scoring scale of the surveyed patients, there was a predominance of patients with severe symptoms obtaining an average score of 25.5 points, followed by moderate symptoms, with an average score of 15.88 points, and finally the average of mild symptoms was 7.33 points. With the previously reported data we can verify the hypothesis, which proposed that there was a higher prevalence of patients with severe symptoms, we found 23 patients with severe symptoms, with a predominant age of 74 years, also, patients with moderate symptoms, were a total of 18 patients, with an average age of 66.4 years.

Graph Number 2. Severity Index of disease

IPSS Score = Mild (0-7) Moderate (8-19) Severe (20-25)
Mild: 9 Moderate: 18 Severe: 23

Graph Number 3. Life quality

Of the 50 patients, those with a degree of satisfaction classified as very dissatisfied predominated (48%), to which 5 points were awarded, followed by patients with a degree of satisfaction defined as fatal, to which 6 points were awarded. Only 8% of the patients were satisfied with their quality of life, a value to which 2 points were awarded.

Regarding the quality of life perceived by patients, the degree of satisfaction with it is described as: Terrible, very dissatisfied, dissatisfied, indifferent, satisfied, and very satisfied, each of which is given a score: 6 for terrible, 5 for very dissatisfied, 4 for dissatisfied, 3 for indifferent, 2 for satisfied, and 1 for very satisfied. Patients who felt very dissatisfied with their quality of life predominated, with 24 patients (48%) and only 4 patients (8%) who were satisfied with their quality of life, and none were found to be very satisfied.

An association was performed using the ANOVA test and by Tuckey's multiple comparison test to identify the association between the degree of severity of the patients and the degree of satisfaction, as well as between the degree of severity and the time of consumption of the medication of patients with mild symptoms, where we obtained a statistically significant relationship between patients with Mild symptoms and the degree of satisfaction, obtaining a $P < 0.0001$ as in the association between Mild symptoms and years of consumption, where a $P < 0.0001$ was also obtained.

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Table Number1. Life quality, severity and treatment.

Tuckeys Comparison Test	Means Difference	IC 95,00%	P
Severity and Satisfaction Degree	2,667	-3,892 -1,441	<0,0001
Severity and Years in Tamsulosin Treatment	4,000	-5,225 -2,775	<0,0001
Satisfaction Degree and Years in Tamsulosin Treatment	1,333	0,1080 -	0,0311

With a difference in means of 2.667 for patients with Mild symptoms and the degree of satisfaction, 4.00 for patients with mild symptoms and years of treatment with tamsulosin, and a difference of 1.333 for the degree of satisfaction and years of consumption of tamsulosin, with an average consumption of 4.98 years of treatment.

. For example, patients with mild symptoms showed greater satisfaction with their quality of life. This was associated with a shorter time consuming the drug.

An association was also established for patients classified as having mild symptoms. Severity was associated with satisfaction, severity with years of tamsulosin use.

A Significant associations were found for all outcomes evaluated, with P values of <0.0001 for severity versus satisfaction, P values of <0.0001 for severity versus years of tamsulosin treatment, and P values of 0.0311 for satisfaction versus years of tamsulosin treatment. A total of 9 patients were classified as having mild symptoms, with an average duration of the drug of 4.98 years and persistent mild symptoms. This also represented a significant difference, with a P value of <0.0001 as we represent in table number one.

Graph Number 4. Age and Severity

Regarding the age of the patients, an association was performed using the ANOVA test to determine if there was a statistically significant difference between the age of the

patients and the severity according to the IPSS scale, where patients with severe symptoms were older, with an average age of 74 years, followed by patients with mild symptoms, who had an average age of 71.3 years, and patients with Moderate symptoms had an average of 66.4 years, when performing the ANOVA test, a statistically significant association was found between the ages of patients with moderate symptoms and patients with severe symptoms, obtaining a P value of 0.0148.

Regarding the additional question, we found that of the total sample, 23 patients (46%) would not undergo surgical treatment if the option were available, while 27 patients (54%) expressed their desire to undergo transurethral resection of the prostate if the option were available, also in this same group.

Likewise, of the total number of patients who did not wish to undergo surgical treatment, those with moderate symptoms predominated, with a total of 11 patients (47%), followed by patients with severe symptoms, of which a total of 7 (30%), and finally those with mild symptoms, of which 5 patients (21%), as represented in Figure 5.

Graph Number 5. Surgical Treatment interest

In relation to the added question, we found that of the total sample, 23 patients (46%) would not like to undergo surgical treatment if they had the option, while 27 patients (54%) expressed their desire to undergo transurethral prostatic resection if they had the option, in turn from this same group.

III. DISCUSSION

Among the patients surveyed using the IPSS, the majority remained in moderate and severe stages, accounting for 82% of the sample, while only 18% were classified as having mild symptoms according to the IPSS scale. The mean duration of tamsulosin treatment in these patients was 4.98 years. These findings contrast with literature reports by Masumori et al. (Mexican Journal of Urology, 2019), which indicate that treatment of BPH with alpha-1 adrenergic blockers like tamsulosin can reduce the IPSS by an average of 5 points, suggesting that long-term prescription may be unnecessary. However, in the present study, older patients persisted with severe symptoms.

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Tamsulosin, an alpha-1 adrenergic blocker, constitutes a cornerstone in BPH management and effectively reduces irritative symptoms in patients with good adherence. Nevertheless, long-term monotherapy may not be sufficient to achieve optimal prognosis.

Masumori et al., in their study titled “*Tamsulosin as Initial Therapy for Patients with Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia*”, included 112 patients with IPSS ≥ 8 , the threshold for initiating pharmacological therapy. Over a 5-year follow-up with periodic evaluations, 78 patients (69.9%) discontinued treatment, 21 patients (18.8%) experienced therapeutic failure, and only 34 patients (30.4%) maintained or reduced their IPSS to a mild stage. In our study, results were similar: only 9 patients (18%) achieved maintenance or reduction of their IPSS after tamsulosin treatment, with a mean treatment duration of 4.98 years.

Regarding the age of symptom onset and severity in BPH, older patients exhibited more severe symptoms, with a mean age of 74 years for those with severe symptoms. This aligns with findings by Wang W et al. in an Asian meta-analysis (*Prevalence of Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia in Mainland China*), which included 14 articles and 19 datasets, showing that men aged 70–79 had the highest prevalence of severe symptoms.

Concerning perceived quality of life, there was a predominance of patients reporting being very dissatisfied, totaling 24 patients (48%), followed by those reporting extremely poor satisfaction (11 patients, 22%). Only 4 patients (8%) reported satisfaction with their quality of life. These results are consistent with findings by Martinez M et al., in a cross-sectional study of 339 patients at UMF No.161, IMSS, Mexico City, where mild symptoms were most common (42.2%), followed by moderate (36%) and severe (21.8%). Among patients with severe symptoms, 86.4% reported poor quality of life, similar to our study, where 87.9% of severe cases reported reduced quality of life.

Surgical treatment remains the most effective option for resolving LUTS. However, undergoing transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP) does not guarantee a complete cure but achieves higher success rates compared to pharmacological measures in patients with severe symptoms, effectively improving IPSS scores. Soum D et al. Reported that tamsulosin monotherapy reduces symptoms by 34%, whereas bipolar TURP achieves approximately 80% resolution.

These findings align with our study population, where 14 patients (28%) had previously undergone TURP and opted not to undergo further surgery, continuing tamsulosin with a mean duration of 5.15 years due to dissatisfaction with prior intervention.

IV.CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the findings confirms that age is associated with greater severity of urinary symptoms in BPH. However,

advanced age does not preclude patients from presenting only mild symptoms, reflecting the clinical heterogeneity of the disease.

Regarding therapeutic response, long-term tamsulosin use showed clear limitations. Although some patients treated for more than three years achieved good symptom control, this group was a minority. The majority remained with moderate to severe symptoms, even after nearly five years of use, demonstrating that pharmacological therapy does not always reduce the condition to mild stages but often merely maintains partial symptom control.

Thus, greater symptom severity correlates with lower likelihood of adequate control with medical treatment and a higher probability of requiring surgical intervention. In this context, TURP remains the most effective therapeutic alternative for patients in whom pharmacological management is insufficient. However, myths and fears continue to hinder acceptance, with anxiety and indifference toward surgery being the most prevalent barriers.

The clinical course of BPH indicates that while tamsulosin can stabilize primarily irritative symptoms, it does not provide long-term efficacy and is not recommended as a sole long-term therapy. Disease progression often necessitates surgical intervention, highlighting the importance of timely identification of candidates for this approach to optimize outcomes and improve functional prognosis.

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